

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN HYPERCRIMINALIZATION IN AMERICAN SECONDARY
SCHOOLS AND ACADEMIC RETENTION RATES OF HISPANIC STUDENTS

by

Vicente Rodriguez

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Dr. Alejandro Jose Gradilla, Department of Chicano and Chicana Studies

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Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University, Honors Program

Abstract:

Contextualizing the history of physical and structural violence perpetrated against Hispanic individuals, this project examines how factors of criminalization imposed upon Latino males in secondary schools have a consequent effect on their representation in higher education. Using secondary research data, the findings indicate that school retention rates are drastically affected by the presence of punitive measures, increased surveillance, and systemic prejudicial perceptions imposed by school personnel. Through the observations of researchers and conceptual frameworks, it is found that schools that have a large student body of Hispanic students concurrently have more officers employed and that these students disproportionately receive punitive measures relative to their peers. In this realm, a cohesive mapping of the future of multicultural education is revealed in which educators and policymakers can retaliate against structural violence so that minority students are able to have equitable access to education. I hope that in my future career as an educator, I can provide a glimmer of hope for these students who have consistently been told otherwise. As a proud Latino who is the son of a victim of the system, this project is the essence of my pursuit of higher education as an outlier in a biased track system.

Overview:

The Hispanic population historically has underachieved in the realm of academic retention and graduation rates relative to other ethnic groups. Within the Hispanic population, Latino males achieve less than their female counterparts. Through my research, I attempt to connect the traces of imposing criminalizing factors upon Latino students in secondary school to the consequent school retention rates. While also providing a historical context to unjustified

violence perpetrated against Latinx individuals. This showcases the evidence of systemic racist foundations contributing to the lack of representation of Latino males in higher education relative to their academic peers.

Hypothesis:

Should the disproportionate prevalence of criminalization factors such as increased officer numbers, enhanced surveillance, and punitive measures be performed upon Hispanic students at a higher rate than their peers, then their school retention rates will be negatively affected.

Methods:

I utilized a literary review of multiple secondary documents to analyze the perceived state of hypercriminalization imposed upon Hispanic students. I began by contextualizing the history of violence against Hispanics, present in overt physical forms such as lynchings and forced sterilizations but also through covert structural forms such as deficit thinking and systemic racism. These coalesce in permeating generations and structure by inserting itself against Hispanic students in the realm of academia. Hispanic representation in higher education is miniscule relative to their peers, so examination was conducted in the formative years of a student's time, secondary education. There is something that occurs in this transitory period from adolescence to adulthood that negatively affects future retention rates. I looked at studies conducted that measured the amount of officers enrolled, punitive measures enacted, and concurrent graduation rates at schools that had a large Hispanic student body compared to schools that did not.

Results:

Hispanic students are disproportionately more likely to receive punitive measures from school administrators. Hispanic students who also are English Second Language learners receive more punishment as a compounding effect. Hispanic students are more likely to be situated in the low socioeconomic class, compounded with students in that low socioeconomic class are less likely to attain higher education

Conclusion:

Hispanic students are continuously subjected to the ramifications of prejudicial systemic racism in the realm of education. Hegemonic structural presences are impactful by making Hispanic students believe this vigilant and punitive state is normal for them. School retention rates and representation decreases amongst the Hispanic student population as education level increases.

Future Work:

After graduating CSUF, I will be studying Comparative and International Education while attaining a MSc in Education at the University of Oxford. I will be examining what policy and theoretical changes can be done in the educational journey to enact change for students in their academic process.

The disparities in socioeconomic status, treatment, and perception of minorities are apparent in the many news incidents that have been publicized in recent memory. In looking deeper into the comparisons between minorities and their more privileged counterparts, it is clear that this divide is not limited to the job market or crime rates as some might suggest. It is a fact that all children are different, but all children also progress through some form of education, whether it be private or public. There is an issue in contemporary education regarding the disparity of academic retention rates amongst students of color compared to their white and asian scholarly peers. There is an evident relationship to be seen when it comes to observing the number of minorities enrolled in secondary education and the number registered in post-secondary education. Specifically, the question is raised as to why Latinx and Black students graduate both high school and college at a lesser rate than their peers. There is a structural fault evident within the education system that suppresses the educational prospects of students of color. Systemic racism has propagated a state of hypercriminalization upon minorities, which has transformed from overt, violent acts of discrimination into covert, detrimental forms in the way that students of color experience schooling. The ramifications of this imposed state of criminalization has a negative effect on the consequent graduation and retention rates of these minority students.

The notion of criminalization of Latinx individuals is not a recently theorized notion, as the linear framework of violence has been cataloged and recorded across history. In recent modern history, discrimination has intensified amongst Latinx people, and it is important to look back on how that internalized violence has been projected over time. In particular, Latinx immigrants in contemporary media are being criminalized and have been made victims of

prejudicial mindsets. This is seen with the political debates concerning Deferred Action for Childhood Arrivals (DACA) and the unruly animalistic herding of Latinx migrants in caged detention centers at the borders. There is also the subjugation of Latina women in factories with poor working conditions that endanger the lives of workers, something that the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) has encouraged with its renewed prioritization of outsourced labor. It is imperative to contextualize the progression and transfiguration of violence from outright physical forms to subtle forms that are disguised by the power of systemic racism. In the late 19th century to the early 20th century, there were lynchings and mob killings of Latinx men and women, often acted upon baseless, presumptuous claims. Historical empirical data is weaved together with narrative contexts in *Forgotten Dead: Mob Violence against Mexicans in the United States, 1848-1928*, written by William D. Carrigan and Clive Webb, in which they detail a research study spanning eighty years of violence against Mexicans. In this eighty-year span, there were 547 recorded victims of mob killings, but the actual number including unreported or missing Latinx individuals is thought to be in the thousands (Carrigan & Webb, 5). All of the killings were ‘justified’ through the guise of unsubstantiated accusations of illegal activities. The importance of setting the starting date of survey research at 1848 is because that is the end of the Mexican-American War with the signing of the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo, which saw American presence take control of governmental proceedings. This allowed hegemonic white people, most with racialized views of Latinx people, into positions of power and authority that condoned the use of violence and degradation that has continued to be perpetuated throughout the years. It is also important to note that in the pairs’ introduction in *Forgotten Dead*, the research study’s spans to 1928 not because that is when the lynchings ceased to exist, but rather the publicity of them became negated with more scrutinized legal proceedings. The hateful

sentiments were still harbored in the minds of racists and bigots, only curbing their inhibitions for the fear of persecution.

However, just because public lynchings were pushed out of practice does mean that Latinx bodies were not harmed any longer. In the sphere of medicine in particular, there were deliberate attempts to subvert Latinx bodily autonomy through medical malpractice that purposefully took advantage of language barriers present. The prejudicial mindsets of the prior years did not fade away, and instead found themselves installed in positions of power spread across influential institutions. In the documentary *No Mas Bebés*, the story revolves around the Madrigal vs. Quilligan court case that saw Latinx women retaliating against medical professionals for violating their rights. Thousands of Latinx women were medically sterilized without their knowing consent, and were taken advantage of their inability to speak English, signing forms that were handed to them after enduring childbirth. This was a form of medical coercion done by ‘professionals’ in medicine that exercised the outdated practice of the eugenics movement, motivated by believing that Latinx individuals were of an inferior race. Latinx people have continuously been made victims of crimes solely because of nationality, skin color, cultural values, practices, and English proficiency. It was found by the Madrigal vs. Quilligan that the doctors’ actions were upheld by law because the Latinx women signed the forms, even with the context behind the distribution of the papers. It was a furthering of the notion that medical professionals dehumanized Latinx families because their size was not deemed conventional, and they needed to intervene by forcefully sterilizing them. It is forever a horrific reminder that racism can and will be upheld if the hegemonic majority lets it.

So, an important way to combat this is by directly challenging the established status quo and uplift Latinx individuals into positions of power to enact direct change. A pathway to make

this transition accessible is through education, echoing schooling pioneer Horace Mann in that “education is the great equalizer” and permits the foundation needed to facilitate social and economic mobility. But, in the present day, another form of systemic racism is present in the education system within the United States that displaces Mann’s inspiring quote. Through collected data surveys and collection, it has been found that Latinx students, as well as Black students, have less academic success than their peers at a constant rate that has been sustained for a number of years. In examining why this happens, there are patterns that develop that correlate to an increased prevalence of policing figures in academic settings predominantly across schools with minority student populations. This poses negative ramifications for the future academic prospects of these students in a concept called hypercriminalization that is elaborated upon with the assistance of a multitude of articles, databases, and research.

Analyzing and diagnosing forms of hypercriminalization amongst secondary schools is of the utmost importance because of the implications that hindrances to development pose for an adolescent's future. Adolescence is where the stigma against students of color is indoctrinated into young, impressionable minds. Images of a model minority as well as a stigmatized stereotypical minority can be implanted and reinforced at a young age through the educational system. Focusing on the latter, this effect is generated by a state of hypercriminalization that influences the lives of black and brown youth, in the case of this discussion, specifically young Latinx males. Moreover, immigrant youth often face heightened scrutinization because of the publicized and controversial nature of its discussion in mainstream media. These groups suffer more from the concept because the disassociation with school pushes these youth out of the education system. The American Latinx population is also projected to be the majority ethnic group of the U.S. population by 2045, so the examination of how the system will affect a large

part of our future demographic is essential. The pushouts then flow into complex institutions like prisons, technical schools, and the workforce. The effects that the imposed hypercriminalized state of Latinx youth has on the realm of academia's prospects for higher education is detrimental. Not only are the aspirations of the youth damaged, but the influence of systemic racism is perpetuated.

The primary mission is to investigate the correlation between the concept of an imposed hypercriminalized state on minority Latinx youth and the consequent effect of the disproportionate representation of minorities in higher education. This specific issue stems from the apparent lack of minority representation, specifically Latinx students, in higher education past high school in both the realms of faculty and student. This concept is seen in the basic levels of education as the proportion of Latinx retention rates decrease as the level of education increases. When looking at the National Center for Education Statistics for public secondary schools from the U.S. Department of Education, Hispanics and Blacks, 82% and 80% respectively, had less graduation percentage than Whites (89%) and Asians (93%) in the 2018-2019 school year. There was also a decrease in college graduation rates amongst Hispanic and Black students compared to their academic peers. It is imperative to understand what happens in this transitory stage of adolescence where students are entering the next phase of their lives, but the fact of the matter is that this inverse relationship has a direct causal effect on the policies of American educational institutions. There is certainly an effect that a constant state of scrutinizing supervision and policing has on the rate of school retention and incarceration, leading to a reduction of the Latinx population in school demographics. An imposed state of hypercriminalization placed upon minorities by law enforcement in educational establishments is a root cause of these statistical disparities.

This topic has mass importance because it has so many implications to explain the many disparities among minorities in the spheres of affluence, socioeconomic standing, occupation, and education. There is some underlying cause that permeates the substance of society that allows the collaboration of suppression and oppression in the form of microaggressions that allow subtle discrimination to remain intact. There has always been a history of violence against minority communities, whether it be physical violence or, in this case, structural violence. But the dangers that exist for Latino males, in particular, are the constant stereotyping and hypercriminalized state that these boys seem to live in. The concept of hypercriminalization is a required term due to its place in the fundamentals of the argument. Victor Rios, in his book *Punished: Policing the Lives of Black and Latino Boys*, describes hypercriminalization as a process through which daily activities are scrutinized and viewed prejudicially, usually being met with punitive measures (Rios xiv). Hypercriminalization becomes integral as the very nature of its conceptualized existence creates these added forms of punishment enforcements against the minority community within educational institutions. There are terms like "going-dumb" and "dummy smart," the former Rios describes as an agent of minority boys to empower themselves against authority figures in resisting restraints (Rios 119). As for "dummy smart," this was another tactic for defying authority on the terms of the oppressed, playing into the 'fears' of the authority figures and essentially taking the narrative into their own hands. Their lives become about existing and surviving amongst a broken system in the forms of "acting tough" or "going dumb," tactics that Victor Rios cites as defense mechanisms to endure. The terms and concepts that Rios introduces apply as they all define the Latinx youth experience by navigating different modes of cultural survival. The stakes are so dire because of the rampant racialization in schools to see how strongly the hegemonic majority has socially constructed a notion about minority

students. Specifically, minority students are seen as needing help and “at-risk,” which further puts them down as a troubled student, all of this being used as descriptors without even looking at the child for what they offer in the classroom through grades, writing, or oral discussions.

Society's means of enforcing and upholding ideals that lie subtly underneath the surface still permeates the mainframe of our daily lives through these structural differences. School as both an environment and a place for learning intertwines in a malignant way with the introduction of hypercriminalization as a form of structural violence present.

Hypercriminalization is a morphing concept, and it is not only seen in the form of physical law enforcement presence on school campuses. Hypercriminalization is also evident in the way that surveillance is increased on minority students, K-9 searches, metal detectors, stop and frisks, threats of deportation from Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE), and even booking stations on school grounds. Minority students experience these circumstances at a disproportionate rate on school grounds, a place that is supposedly dedicated towards the fostering of educational prospects. American institutions dehumanize Latinx students in this process in the way that students in secondary schools are responded to amidst suspicion. Rios's *Punished* is a method to bring crucial awareness to a harsh reality while also providing a glimmer of hope when stacked against the odds. Jeff Duncan-Andrade's “Growing Roses in Concrete” TED talk is also highly indicative of the endurance that children in low-socioeconomic areas are equipped with. Both scholars elaborate on the defensive maneuvers that minority students often develop because of the lack of moral support they receive from both educators and administrators. Instead, it brings focus on the punitive measures that students receive within these schools, and how minority students are often the victim in these scenarios. The concept of a "school-to-prison pipeline" is built upon these notions of diminished

foundational repercussions for ‘misbehaving’ minority students within the education system, as minority students are disproportionately more likely to enter the judicial system at an earlier age than their peers. Additionally, a dissertation by Emily Nunez-Eddy builds upon this notion as it presents a "school-prison nexus" in hypothesizing that the pathway is not linear and has many different stipulations in store. Nunez-Eddy’s theorization indicates that discipline policies within schools have a large part in determining which students will progress to attain higher education.

In the context of the education establishments, it is astounding to see just how prevalent incarceration is within American society. For instance, the *Prison Policy Initiative* website has a page titled, “States of Incarceration: The Global Context 2021,” which showcases just how domineering the United States is with incarceration in comparison to the rest of the world. Not only is the United States the leading global figure in incarceration rates per 100,000 people, totaling at 664, but thirty-four states rank above the second-closest global country. In fact, per 2020 data reports, one out of every five prisoners in the world is imprisoned within the United States. From data collected from the Federal Bureau of Prisons database, it is alarming to see that Hispanics make up 30.2% of all inmates, with a total of close to 48,000 inmates. Even more so, there are over two million people in the incarceration system itself across all U.S. prisons, jails, and judicial facilities. For many of these inmates, there are potentially disastrous implications that result after their first recorded arrest. Within the same *Prison Policy Initiative* site, the article “Arrest, Release, Repeat: How police and jails are misused to respond to social problems” written by Alexi Jones and Wendy Sawyer states that “at least 1 in 4 of those individuals are booked into jail more than once during the same year.” Moreover, of these individuals who were arrested multiple times, 36% of them did not graduate secondary school. There is a skewed number of repeat offenders, who are referred to as “frequent utilizers” because in the prison

system, they attain benefits that they do not receive outside such as health care, food, and shelter. Regardless, having an arrest on one's record can be harmful to job prospects as many businesses are reluctant to hire applicants with marks on their legal record. This is determined by a manner of deficit thinking that is also present within education, as prejudicial mindsets about certain individuals are decided because of predestined notions about one's character.

Aside from that, there is also the influence that school police, punitive measures, and enforcement have on the mental psyche of students and their consequent performance in school. There is pressure for them to perform and, if not, pressure to quickly get a job or help out with costs at home due to the disparities of generally being located within a lower socioeconomic class contributed to the globalized capitalist society that we live in and the opportunities that they exploit. Bringing awareness and comprehension to a complex subject that has implications for the way we perceive society and the interactions between privileged and unprivileged individuals in a school nexus. Secondary schools and their policies surrounding the disciplinary measures taken out against minority students is suggestive of discriminatory practices on a large scale of educational institutions. The role of school in children's lives and how their learning and experiences impact their future is monumental, so when school administration and police enforce these rules and regulations that suppress minority males by categorizing them into a negative perception, it has detrimental effects. The articles "School Strictness and Education: Investigating Racial and Ethnic Educational Inequalities Associated with Being Pushed Out" and "Latino/a Student Misbehavior and School Punishment" are both critical pieces to this correlation made between minorities and school retention factors. The "School Strictness and Education" article investigates the propensity correlation between ethnicity and the severity of punitive measures taken against them in schools. The researchers use statistical data that

incorporates the students' location and ethnicity to see the various relationships that exist in determining school success amongst school punishment. Along with another article, "School Punishment and Education: Racial/Ethnic Disparities with Grade Retention and the Role of Urbanicity," it is determined that minority students situated across all settings between urban, suburban, and rural schools experienced less retention rates than their peers.

In addition, the article "Latino/a Student Misbehavior and School Punishment" focuses on one specific ethnicity in that of the Latino/a population. The article is written by a pair of researchers that sought to investigate the notion of the last article of school misbehavior and their consequent punishment in the lens of looking at the Latino/a population. The pair of Anthony Peguero and Zahra Shekarkhar used empirical data of orchestrating an observational study that factored in different identity aspects of the given student population, such as gender and ethnicity. The sample size and duration of the study may not have been extended or large enough for some researchers to provide a cumulative assessment of the data. Still, the results do make for an intriguing inquiry. The study concluded that Latino/a students were not misbehaving more than their White peers, but the punitive measures taken against them were projected at a higher rate. This sort of disproportionate percentage of punitive measures is alarming and indicative of an engrained educational doctrine that has had a tainted past of perpetuating a malignant stereotype of minority students. This is apparent in the rates of school retention and the disproportionate levels of school retention among Latino males compared to other ethnicities. The school violence and school strictness articles are crucial in comprehending the issue and how it pertains to these individuals. Of course, many other factors come into play, but when faced with microaggressions from educators and those employed by the education system, it directly plays a role in driving these students away from schooling.

School's punitive measures and strictness levels enacted upon students have long-lasting effects in their goals for educational prosperity. Because of the deliverance of the punishments associated with administrative decisions such as detentions, suspensions, and expulsions, students are pushed further from the educational track at a young age. This correlation is delineated by a team of researchers in the article "Tipping Point: Effect of the Number of In-school Suspensions on Academic Failure," in which they studied first-year freshman high schoolers in Texas public schools with analyzing both the amount of suspensions as well as failure in state-mandated standardized tests. The results of the study found that just one singular suspension is linked to a 25% risk of academic failure on the standardized test, along with this risk being more prevalent in minority student populations. In particular, Black students were suspended two to four times the rate of their white peers, while Latinx students were suspended at twice the rate (Blake, et al, 2021). This has consequences for minority student performance in academic settings, as the time spent in suspensions also takes away from time in classrooms, with academic peers, and their educators. Disciplinary procedures like these are harmful because it displaces students of color from education, and places them on a track with demerits on their record, punished rather than supported. This disengagement from education has an effect in making them reluctant to carry on with their studies, because along with a negative effect on their grade point averages (GPA), this also causes an increased likelihood in dropping out of high school and delayed graduation, if they choose to stay. There is a clear connection between suspensions and negative academic outcomes, and examining minority student experiences can adjust the way that policymakers adhere to the current system and its faulty ways.

There is an established connection between suspensions and decreased academic success, but it is important to realize just how predisposed minority students are exposed to this sort of

degrading treatment. Within the *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law*, Barbara Robles-Ramamurthy and Clarence Watson speak about minority experiences in education in “Examining Racial Disparities in Juvenile Justice.” The pair find that minority students are more likely to be situated in schools that enforce a zero-tolerance policy. What this means is that students are pushed out of the school system by suspension and expulsion for students who commit ‘misconduct.’ Combined with the fact that minority students are more likely to receive punitive disciplinary measures, Latinx and Black students are predominantly targeted in this policy manner. Also, these students are more likely to be arrested at a young age because of these zero-tolerance procedures, which has harrowing effects upon their re-entry into education, as a majority stay linked to the judicial system. When looking at Figure 3, “Percentage of public schools that took a serious disciplinary action, by selected school characteristics: School year 2019-20” in the National Center of Educational Statistics provided by the U.S. Department of Education, it is found that public schools with a majority population of students of color experience more punitive measures taken. Schools experienced serious disciplinary actions 39.8% of the time when they had a student population of over 76% students of color. Conversely, when a school has a student population of less than or equal to 25% students of color, they experienced serious disciplinary actions 31.2% of the time. Almost a 10% gap between predominantly non-students of color schools and students of color schools. There is also the matter of the 14% disparity between schools that have students that qualify for free or reduced lunch and those that do not. If a student qualifies for free and reduced lunch, that indicates that they are situated in a lower socioeconomic class. The same data table indicates that students in schools with a majority of students are eligible for free and reduced lunch experience disciplinary measures at an increased rate than other schools. This shows that schools’

experience with discriminatory policies is also linked to the financial standing of both the school and its student body. This dilemma poses serious questions for policymakers, as they attempt to grapple with community investment to make it less likely that minority students come into contact with the criminal justice system in the first place. And if they do, what measures can they take to help aid re-entry and end a vicious cycle of incarceration that affects so many others than just the one booked.

This discussion brings in the Anthony Peguero article that looks at the effect of immigration status on the propensity of school violence in the community. "Is Immigrant Status Relevant in School Violence Research? An Analysis With Latino Students" brings additional substance as to why school retention and school violence rates seem to be disproportionate to their peers due to the role of immigration. This article is fixated on the particular cases of just Latinx students, as the issue of immigration status is dominated by concerns over the documentation of Hispanic and Latinx individuals coming from Central and South America. Peguero lines up his evidence with numerical statistical data and cites a sample size of a little more than 1,500 students. The study's results found that students who identified as immigrants, had family members as immigrants, and English being a second language were more prone to becoming a victim of school violence. This is substantial to another case of stigmatization within the Latinx community in a school environment. In reference to the article, "Context of Reception and School Violence: Exploring Nexus of Immigration, Race/Ethnicity, Place, and School Crime," researchers found immigrant students were of particularly vulnerable stages because of their already weakened disposition in regard to feeling comfortable in a different educational setting. Disciplinary measures further aggravate this relationship and put migrant students in a displaced situation within educational contexts.

Looking deeper, it seems like a negative aura about immigrants generated by the fervor of national media coverage and politicians. This contributes to a heightened propensity for discrimination and intolerance against a group of people that directly correlates to student academic success. The entire basis of the claim is that the existence of discrimination and students being criminalized and subjugated plays a role in determining why there is a misrepresentation of minority males in higher education. This adds a nuanced layer particular to the Latinx community as many students either live with immigrant family members or are immigrants themselves. Criminalization factors are apparent in the education system that prevents some students from progressing along the education track, sometimes even through the method of direct removal. ICE's recent scrutiny over its apprehension and detention policies, in which Latinx families and individuals were locked in cages, has prompted many detainees to be released. Yet, this has not stopped the organization from continuing to criminalize Latinx migrants, in which they free detainees on "conditional release," constraining them to an app called SmartLINK or physical ankle monitors. As of June of last year, ICE had about 230,000 people registered under their surveillance programs, which has enabled the government to unjustly pry into matters of violating privacy and intruding itself by recording audio without user consent (Neito del Rio, 2022). This methodology, although not used in schools, is an example of how hegemonic structures employ coercion to impose their will and beliefs upon victimized Latinx populations, regardless of the legitimacy of their fears.

Specifically, in the demographic of Latinx young adults, there are a myriad of ways to be affected in the classrooms and their neighborhoods by a policing system. In the stage of adolescence in Latino males' lifetimes, there are policing factors set in place within the education system that provide hindrances to educational growth and lifetime achievement. School retention

rates affect the rates of minority representation in higher education, and there is a disproportionate number of Latino males represented in institutions of higher learning. Despite the impediments to educational growth through this school-to-prison pipeline and expanding exploitation of students, there lie cracks where individuals escape the traps set up for minority communities. In this, minority individuals are able to reach high occupational positions in higher education, either in the student or faculty population. Although, the number of minority faculty members is also fewer than their peers because the decreased retention numbers affects the amount of individuals that attain their credentials from higher education programs. This is where the inclusion of commercialized exploitation enters the fray because as minorities are not equipped with the status and knowledge of higher education, they are relegated to jobs that do not provide high-paying wages. This number of people becomes stratified even further when looking specifically at the Latino male population. The numbers across the board indicate systemic failure, especially when comparing incarceration and graduation rates.

It is vital that Latinx students have people that look like them represented in secondary and higher education faculty, as it provides an immeasurable moral boost letting them know that higher education is in fact attainable. The influx of multicultural educators not only serves as a way to provide an indirect role as a guide, but also as a direct role as a mentor, providing help to students along their educational journey. This presence is invaluable to the student's school experience, and has a chance to be extremely impactful as they progress through the course of their academic studies. In the topic of minority faculty and creating areas to facilitate better the growth and education of these minority individuals, Gina Ann Garcia's work *Becoming Hispanic-serving institutions: opportunities for colleges and universities* offers a highly detailed guide. Garcia's book looks at institutional building and provides examples of how universities

and colleges can make themselves more inclusive to the community to provide opportunities and role models for those who lack them. Along with Tara Yosso's *Critical Race Counterstories Along the Chicana, Chicano Educational Pipeline*, which both characterize essential developments throughout the educational lifespan of the Latinx population of both students and faculty. Yosso forms complex discussions about the relationship between minority communities and the field of academia, with different circumstances for both books. With a majority of the Latinx population failing to reach higher stages of learning because of the inherent imbalances of the system in which they inhabit. Although there is hope for those still stuck in these perpetual structural violations, the sources provide glimmers of hope and condemnation of the system. Through the use of mentorship, inclusion, and reduction of policies seen as detrimental to the growth of minorities, there can be a potential buffer installed to protect minority students from criminalization threats.

Now that the diagnosis of the issue has been made, it is up to the application of the prognosis to be dealt with in the hands of educators and policymakers who can directly affect educational policy implementation. There needs to be an eradication of the notion of deficit thinking in the minds of teachers that have a highly influential role in the way that students act and perceive themselves. At a young age, this can be greatly deleterious in the form of the Pygmalion Effect, a psychological concept that suggests that expressing low expectations to a group leads to a worse performance. However, the inverse is also true, in which expressing high expectations to a group or individual leads to a better performance. In an academic setting, this falls upon the role of the authority figure of the classroom, the teacher, and it is up to them to uphold standards for all members of the student body. A student's failing grade is no longer to be seen as a normality in their race or culture, nor does a student's exceptional performance is to be

seen as an abnormality. These misconceptions are false truths that have been propagated throughout the years because of the held notions heralded as truth within academia. This type of hegemonic structural presence is a contributing limiting factor as to why Latinx students were seen to have been predestined to not achieve higher education.

Work has been done to reverse the effects from years of systemic transgressions against minorities because these same suppressed individuals are achieving unprecedented heights in capabilities that were previously of diminished value. In recent data collected from the National Center of Education Statistics and the Department of Education, it was found that the overall dropout rate decreased from 7.4% in 2010 to 5.3% in 2020. Additionally, Latinx dropout rates decreased from 15.1% to 7.4% over this ten-year period, an illuminating figure that details that the efforts that have been published and broadcasted have not been in vain. Putting this number in perspective with the help of John Gramlich's *Pew Research Center* piece, "Hispanic dropout rate hits new low, college enrollment at new high," it is a huge mark of improvement from 1996's 34% secondary school dropout rate. Also, there is an improvement in the amount of Latinx students enrolled in college currently than there were in the early 2000s. Both of these figures are signals that Latinx students are becoming increasingly representative in education, and are budding scholars that will attain higher education. This results in a likelihood to progress in upward social mobility through the prospective economic openings that arrive concurrent with elevated education. Still, the system is flawed and there are disparities present which pose negative hindrances for Latinx empowerment, as it is more likely for a Latinx student to be first-generation across all demographics by a wide margin. Mainly because there has already been a set precedent for suppressing minority populations in favor of maintaining the hegemonic status quo. Echoing previous statements, the combating of hegemonic authority is via direct contention

with policies and policymakers that are deemed detrimental to the way of progress. Not only can educators and students become involved, but also citizens that are compelled to fight for a just cause that can impact the lives of innumerable students, both contemporary and future. There are numerous community organizations that provide benefits for Latinx students and budding scholars, in the form of scholarship and fellowship opportunities that offer pathways of success for youth. Along with school board elections and becoming knowledgeable about running candidates, all influential ways that people can change the way that Latinx youth traverse throughout their educational experiences.

The work laid out previously by the researchers is vital in understanding that the stigmatization and suppression placed upon minorities were evident both decades ago as well as in contemporary society. Further research is necessary to analyze the key features of hypercriminalization and its effects on male youth who are more prone to be impacted by it due to outlying factors. The disproportionate number of minority youth that do not pursue higher education has been perpetuated throughout the years. The number of Latinx youth that are currently being violated by the system is large, with an even larger amount that have been wronged previously and discarded by the destructive cycle. Without the collective effort of multiple researchers and those who have made it out of the oppressive system, there will be no reprieve to the injustice that has plagued generations. But, with increased awareness and policy changes, there is courage that the number of those negatively impacted will decrease in the future, and that academic equity can be ushered and practiced within American academic institutions.

Reflection:

The current environment has dramatic implications for those in schooling now, mainly because a particular track record has been sustained due to this conceptualized criminalized state. It has even affected my father, who was pushed out of the education system and into the workforce. He is not and will not be the last Latinx male to fall victim to the structural violence that affected his life, and that is why this research is still necessary today. The hope is that this paper will permeate the academic world, just like one of the sources listed is a published dissertation. Research is conducted for the benefit of other researchers, and the collective studies and their results go a long way in garnering awareness for divisive issues. In looking at the disproportionate number of minorities in higher education, it is imperative to look at some factors that form barriers to the betterment of the minority community to avoid the suppression against them for years. In writing this paper and collecting the data research, I realize that I am an outlier in these findings and that the work that I am researching is my chance to insert myself as an interruption in the biased cycle that is currently at work.

Works Cited

No Mas Bebés. (2015). Dir. Tajima-Pena, R. Perf. Madrigal, D., Hernandez A., Dr.

Rosenfeld, B. Moon Canyon Films, 2015. Film.

Federal Bureau of Prisons.

https://www.bop.gov/about/statistics/statistics_inmate_ethnicity.jsp

National Center for Education Statistics. (2022). Public High School Graduation Rates.

Condition of Education, U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education

Sciences. <https://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/indicator/coi>

National Center for Education Statistics. (2022) Serious Disciplinary Actions Taken by

Public Schools. *Condition of Education*. U.S. Department of Education, Institute

of Education Sciences. [https://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/indicator/a18/serious-](https://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/indicator/a18/serious-disciplinary-actions)

[disciplinary-actions](https://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/indicator/a18/serious-disciplinary-actions)

National Center for Education Statistics. (2022). Status Dropout Rates. *Condition of*

Education. U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences.

<https://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/indicator/coj>

Blake, J., Eason, J. M., Marchbanks, M. P., Peguero, A. A., & Varela, K. S. (2018)

School Punishment and Education: Racial/Ethnic Disparities With Grade

Retention and the Role of Urbanicity. *Urban Education*, Vol. 56 (2). DOI:

10.1177/0042085918801433

Blake, J., Eason, J. M., Marchbanks, M. P., Peguero, A. A., & Varela, K. S. (2017).

School Strictness and Education: Investigating Racial and Ethnic Educational Inequalities Associated with Being Pushed Out. *Sociology of Race and Ethnicity*, 4(2), 261-280. DOI: 10.1177/2332649217730086

Blake, J., Marchbanks, M. P., Ortiz, N. A., Peguero, A. A., Smith, D., & Unni, A. (2021).

Tipping Point: Effect of the Number of In-school Suspensions on Academic Failure. *Contemporary School Psychology*, Vol. 25. DOI: 10.1007/s40688-020-00289-7

Brent, J. J. (2016). Placing the criminalization of school discipline in economic context.

Punishment and Society, 18(5), 521-543. DOI: 10.1177/1462474516642858

Carrigan, W. D., & Webb, C. (2013). *Forgotten Dead: Mob Violence against Mexicans in the United States, 1848-1928*. Oxford University Press.

Chavez, J. M., DiPietro, S. M., Esbensen, F., Peguero, A. A., & Slocum, L. A. (2015).

School Climate and Violence: Does Immigrant Status Matter? *Youth Violence and Juvenile Justice*, 13(4), 299-322. DOI: 10.1177/1541204014547589

Duncan-Andrade, J. (2011). TEDxGoldenGateED - Jeff Duncan-Andrade - Growing

Roses in Concrete. *YouTube*. <https://youtu.be/2CwS60ykM8s>

Dunning-Lozano, J. L., Hong, J., Irizarry, Y., Iwama, J. A., King, S., Peguero, A. A.

(2021). Context of Reception and School Violence: Exploring the Nexus of Immigration, Race/Ethnicity, Place, and School Crime. *Sociology of Race and Ethnicity*, Vol. 7 (3). DOI: 10.1177/2332649220980492

- Garcia, G.A. (2019). *Becoming Hispanic-Serving Institutions: Opportunities for Colleges*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Gramlich, J. (2017). Hispanic dropout rate hits new low, college enrollment at new high. *Pew Research Center*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2017/09/29/hispanic-dropout-rate-hits-new-low-college-enrollment-at-new-high/>
- Gramlich, J. (2020). How border apprehensions, ICE arrests and deportations have changed under Trump. *Pew Research Center*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2020/03/02/how-border-apprehensions-ice-arrests-and-deportations-have-changed-under-trump/>
- Herring, T., & Widra, E. (2021). States of Incarceration: The Global Context 2021. *Prison Policy Initiative*. <https://www.prisonpolicy.org/global/2021.html>
- Hirschfield, P. J. (2008). Preparing for Prison?: The criminalization of school discipline in the USA. *Theoretical Criminology*, 12(1), 79-101. DOI: 10.1177/1362480607085795
- Jones, A., & Sawyer, W. (2019). Arrest, Release, Repeat: How police and jails are misused to respond to social problems. *Prison Policy Initiative*. <https://www.prisonpolicy.org/reports/repeatarrests.html>
- Nieto del Rio, G. M. (2022). Meet SmartLINK, the App Tracking Nearly a Quarter Million Immigrants. *The Markup*. <https://themarkup.org/the->

[breakdown/2022/06/27/meet-smartlink-the-app-tracking-nearly-a-quarter-million-immigrants](#)

Nunez-Eddy, E. (2020). The Coalescence of Education and Criminal Justice in the United States: The School-Prison Nexus and the Prison-Industrial Complex in a Capitalist Society. *Arizona State University*.

Owens, E. G. (2017). Testing the School-to-Prison Pipeline. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 36(1), 11-37. DOI: 10.1002/pam.21954

Peguro, A. A. (2008). Is Immigrant Status Relevant in School Violence Research? An Analysis with Latino Students. *The Journal of School Health*, 78(7), 397-404. DOI: 10.1111/j.1746-1561.2008.00320.x

Peguro, A. A., & Shekarkhar, Z. (2011). Latino/a Student Misbehavior and School Punishment. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 33(1), 54-70. DOI: 10.1177/0739986310388021

Rios, V. (2011). *Punished: Policing the Lives of Black and Latino Boys*. New York University Press.

Robles-Ramamurthy, B., & Watson, C. (2019). Examining Racial Disparities in Juvenile Justice. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law*, Vol. 51 (1).

Yosso, T. J. (2005). *Critical Race Counterstories Along the Chicana, Chicano Educational Pipeline*. Routledge.